

Supplementary Table S2. Media formulation for carbohydrate restricted de Man, Rogosa, and Sharpe media supplemented with ribose (CR-MRS+R). All ingredients were dissolved in water prior to sterilization by autoclaving (121°C, 20 min).

Ingredient	g/L or mL/L	Manufacturer Information
Proteose peptone no. 3	10.0	Hardy Diagnostics (Santa Maria, CA)
Beef extract	10.0	Research Products International (Mt. Prospect, IL)
Yeast extract	5.0	Neogen Culture Media (Lansing, MI)
Sodium acetate	5.0	Fisher Scientific (Fair Lawn, NJ)
Ammonium citrate	2.0	Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO)
Dipotassium phosphate	2.0	Avantor Performance Materials (Radnor, PA)
Magnesium sulfate	0.1	Fisher Scientific (Fair Lawn, NJ)
Manganese sulfate	0.05	Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO)
Tween-80	1.0	Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO)
Ribose	20.0	Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO)
Bacteriological Agar*	15.0	IBI Scientific (Dubuque, IA)

*Agar excluded from formulation when preparing broth medium.